

Expert Interviews on Attribute Validation for a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE)

Interviewee Name:

Company:

Date:

Interviewer:

Dear

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this interview. The interview is conducted as part of my Master's thesis at the University of Applied Sciences BFI Vienna and is embedded in the broader research framework of Denise Beil's PhD project at the University of Antwerp.

Brief Description of the Master's Thesis:

The core focus of my thesis is the empirical preparation of a Stated Preference Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) to analyze decision-making behavior in European freight transport along the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor.

The aim of these expert interviews is to define realistic and practice-relevant value ranges for key transport attributes (costs, transit time, reliability, frequency) and to understand how shippers and logistics service providers (LSPs) evaluate trade-offs between these criteria.

In this interview, we aim to:

- Empirically narrow down the relevant value ranges (min–max spans) for key attributes (costs, transit time, reliability, frequency) and transport modes (road, rail, inland waterway) along selected origin-destination (OD) routes of the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor;
- Validate the composition, interpretation, and perceived importance of these attributes;
- Understand the cognitive decision-making logic of shippers and LSPs regarding trade-offs between attributes;
- Identify critical interactions and threshold values required for modeling realistic DCE choice sets based on ex-ante validated data.

Format & Process:

The interview is **semi-structured**, takes approx. **60 minutes**, and includes both:

- **Tables for quantitative estimation**, and
- **Follow-up questions** on practical relevance and interpretation.

We kindly ask you to review and, if possible, **pre-fill the tables** based on your expertise.

All information will be treated **confidentially and anonymised** and used **exclusively for academic purposes**.

We truly appreciate your time and insights – thank you in advance!

Warm regards,

Henrike Bauer & Denise Beil

1. Company Characteristics (Demographic Context)

Objective: To control for structural influencing factors in later modeling

- Company type (shipper, trade, LSP, carrier, other):

- Company size (number of employees, revenue class, locations):

- Position of interviewee (strategic/operational, dispatch, management):

- Main customers (industry, trade, 3PL, etc.): _____
- Frequency of cross-border transports in the TEN-T Rhine-Danube corridor:

2. Context Screening: Use of Routes

Objective: To ensure full coverage of the five predefined routes

Which of the following Routes (OD routes) are you familiar with or have actively used in the past?

Main transport mode used (Road / Rail / Inland Waterway):

Route	Connection	Countries	Actively used? (Yes/No)
R1	Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (via Stuttgart/München)	FR, DE, AT	
R2	München/Nürnberg – Praha – Žilina – Košice	DE, CZ, SK	
R3	München/Nürnberg – Wien/Bratislava	DE, AT, SK	
R4	Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara	AT, SK HU, RO	
R5	Wien/Bratislava – Constanța	AT, SK, HU, RO	

3. Data Basis for DCE Modelling: Empirical Attribute Assessment Along Defined Relations and Transport Modes

Definition of Attributes & Guide for Interviewees

This interview focuses on four core transport attributes: **transport costs, transit time, reliability, and frequency.**

All values should refer to the **entire door-to-door transport** process between two business locations along the specified routes.

- **For rail and inland waterway transport,** we consider **intermodal freight transport with containerized cargo units**, including pre- and post-haulage by truck.
- **For road transport,** we refer to **classic unimodal trucking, i.e. continuous door-to-door transport.**

Our goal is to ensure that all responses are comparable across modes and reflect the full door-to-door chain.

Attribute Definitions

- **Transport Costs:**
Please provide – if possible – an estimate of **total transport costs** for the full **door-to-door process**. Approximate values and value ranges (preferably in €/tonne-kilometre) are also helpful.
- **Transit Time:**
Refers to the typical total duration from loading at the sender to unloading at the receiver (door-to-door).
- **Reliability:**
Defined as the share of transports that arrive within the **agreed time window.**
- **Frequency:**
Serves as a proxy for flexibility and refers to the realistically feasible **number of departures per week on a given route** – regardless of how many actually take place.

We kindly ask you to review and, if possible, pre-fill the tables based on your expertise for the respective routes and attributes and – based on your experience – **fill in typical, minimum and maximum values.**

This helps us discuss deviations from literature values and special cases in a structured way during the interview.

All ranges and extreme values in the tables are based on recognized scientific studies, EU reports, and official annual reports relevant to the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor and European road freight markets.

Again: All information will be treated confidentially and anonymized and used exclusively for academic purposes.

Why Extreme Values Are Included:

Extreme values (e.g., for cost, time, or reliability) represent rare but real situations—such as fuel price spikes, major strikes, border closures, or extraordinary demand surges—that can temporarily push figures beyond normal market conditions. These help us understand the full range of operational realities and are important for robust modeling.

Examples of Extreme Situation e.g. IWT:

- **Transport Costs (up to 0.150 €/tkm):** Observed during periods of record fuel prices, toll increases, or capacity shortages (e.g., 2022–2023).
- **Transit Time (up to 5 days):** Severe disruptions such as border congestion, strikes, or extreme weather can delay shipments.

R1 – Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (via Stuttgart/München) ca. 650 km

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.060 – 0.120	0.085				0.150
Transit Time (Days)	1 – 3	1.5				5
Reliability (%)	– 98	93				75
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	5 – 7	7				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R2 – München/Nürnberg – Praha – Žilina – Košice ca. 850 km

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.060 – 0.120	0.085				0.150
Transit Time (Days)	1 – 3	1.5				5
Reliability (%)	85 – 98	93				75
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	5 – 7+	7				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R3 – München/Nürnberg – Wien/Bratislava ca. 550 km

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.060 – 0.120	0.085				0.150
Transit Time (Days)	1 – 3	1.5				5
Reliability (%)	85 – 98	93				75
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	5 – 7+	7				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R4 – Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara ca. 550 km

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.060 – 0.120	0.085				0.150
Transit Time (Days)	1 – 3	1.5				5
Reliability (%)	85 – 98	93				75
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	5 – 7+	7				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R5 – Wien/Bratislava – Constanța ca.1350 km

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.060 – 0.120	0.085				0.150
Transit Time (Days)	1 – 3	1.5				5
Reliability (%)	85 – 98	93				75
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	5 – 7+	7				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

4. Attribute-Specific Deep Dive

A1. Key Data on Transport Costs

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

(e.g., seasonal or regional variations, political measures, operational constraints)

What determines the level of transport costs on this relation?

Tolls Energy Labour Handling Equipment Other: _____

How sensitive are shippers to cost differences?

- Very sensitive (even small differences trigger changes)
 Moderately sensitive (only substantial differences have an effect)
 Hardly sensitive (other factors dominate)
 Cannot be answered in general – please explain:

Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ from typical transport costs still realistic in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the relation or transport mode – please comment:

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience
 Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A2. Key Data on Transit Time

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

What are the main factors influencing transit time?

Border crossings Handling Timetables Infrastructure
 Capacity Weather Other: _____

Do shippers require specific delivery time windows (e.g. fixed delivery slots or advance notice)?

How tolerant are your clients towards deviations from the expected transit time?

(e.g. ± 1 day, ± 6 hours)

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical transit times still realistic in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the relation or mode – please comment:

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience
 Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A3. Key Data on Reliability

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

How do you assess the average reliability per mode along the OD relations you use?

Are there significant differences between routes or countries?

Road: _____

Rail: _____

Inland Waterway: _____

Which factors influence reliability along this route?

Weather Terminal procedures Staff availability

IT systems Coordination Other: _____

How do you define punctuality in your daily practice?

Same-day arrival acceptable ± 2 hours tolerance

Pre-agreed delivery window Any deviation is acceptable if consistent

Other: _____

What level of reliability is still acceptable to you? When does it become critical or lead to modal exclusion?

Road: _____

Rail: _____

Inland Waterway: _____

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical reliability rates still plausible in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the route – please comment:

Comment: _____

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience

Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A4. Key Data on Frequency

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

How many departures per week are typical or realistically possible for this mode on this route?

Answer: _____

How stable is this frequency over the year?

(e.g., seasonal variation, capacity constraints, weather-related)

Answer: _____

Which factors influence the regularity of departures?

Seasonal variation Volume of demand Timetable reliability

Staff availability Other: _____

From what minimum frequency onward would you consider a mode suitable for regular use?

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical frequency levels still plausible in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the relation – please comment:

Comment: _____

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience

Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

5. Trade-Offs and Decision Logics

- **Which attribute most strongly influences your modal choice – and why?**

Answer: _____

- **How do you weigh costs vs. transit time? Are there thresholds at which modal shifts become likely?**

Answer: _____

- **To what extent is reliability considered in your operational decisions?**

Answer: _____

- **Which hidden/additional costs affect your decisions (e.g. storage due to delay)?**

Answer: _____

- **What role do political or regulatory factors play (e.g. tolls, CO₂ pricing)?**

Answer: _____

- **What change in an attribute (e.g. -20% cost or +10% reliability) would trigger a realistic shift?**

Answer: _____

- **Are there absolute exclusion criteria (e.g. <60% reliability)?**

Answer: _____

- **How do you prioritise economic vs. temporal and operational attributes?**

Answer: _____

6. Attribute Validation and Additional Aspects

- **Do you feel that any relevant attribute is missing?**

Answer: _____

- **Would you be willing to participate in a pretest of the choice sets with hypothetical scenarios?**

Answer: _____

- **Are there any important aspects that are underrepresented in the modal shift debate?**

Answer: _____

7. Influence of Cargo Type on Transport Mode Choice

Question:

Does the type of cargo you transport influence your choice of transport mode?

If yes: For which of the following cargo types is the choice of transport mode particularly relevant in your decision-making?

(Multiple answers possible)

- High-value goods
- Time-sensitive or perishable goods
- Bulk cargo / high-volume commodities
- No significant difference between cargo types
- Other – please comment: _____

Optional comment:

Reference Values and Sources

All ranges and extreme values in the tables are based on recognized scientific studies, EU reports, and official annual reports relevant to the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor.